

Determination of the transverse width and distance of an object with a smartphone camera

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A smartphone is a powerful learning aid in the hands of a large section of students around the world. The camera of the phone can be used for several learning purposes apart from its obvious purpose of photographing. If the focal length of the lens of the camera can be determined, several experiments in optics can be performed with the camera. In some recent works,^{1,2} the method for determination of the focal length of a smartphone camera has been discussed. These works have shown that if we can determine the magnification of an object, we can find the distance of the object and can verify the lens equation. For this, the size of the object has to be known. In our present work, we have determined the focal length of the lens and have shown that with the knowledge of this we can determine both the transverse size and the distance of an object, by photographing it from two positions, separated by a distance along the line of sight of the camera. It is possible to find the size of the image on the camera sensor in terms of the number of pixels using softwares available freely from the internet. In a few other works,³⁻⁸ the smartphone camera has been utilised for conducting experiments in optics. We have worked with an Apple iphone, Model No. iPhone 12 mini.

Theoretical Background for determining the focal length

When an image is formed by a convex lens, we have the relation^{1,2}

$$\frac{1}{v} - \frac{1}{u} = \frac{1}{f}. \quad (1)$$

Here u is the object distance and v is the image distance measured from the lens which is of negligible thickness. f is the focal length of the lens and is positive

according to our sign convention. When a real image is formed by a convex lens, object and image positions are on the opposite sides of the lens and the image is inverted. Transverse magnification produced by the lens is given by

$$m = \frac{v}{u} = \frac{I}{O} \quad (2)$$

where I and O denote the transverse sizes of the image and the object respectively and the magnification is negative. From the above two equations we have

$$m = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{u}{f}}. \quad (3)$$

Inverting this equation we get

$$f = \frac{u}{\frac{1}{m} - 1}. \quad (4)$$

While calculating f using Eq.(4), u and m are negative according to our sign convention. So,

$$f = \frac{|u|}{\frac{1}{|m|} + 1}. \quad (5)$$

We take the photograph of a ruler kept at a known distance. So the distance between any two marks on the ruler is known. By analyzing the photograph with Microsoft Paint software, one can find the difference of pixel numbers at the two ends of a selected part of the image. This difference is what we have termed pixel diff. in Tables I and II. The idea about pixels can be found in greater detail in the article by Jesus J.Barreiro et al.⁹ The length of 1 pixel was found from the website^{10,11} relevant for our camera. We call it R and for our phone R was $1.4\mu\text{m}$. The image size is $R \times$ pixel diff. We determine the magnification m and hence the focal length f_c of the camera lens using Eq.(5). In Table I we have presented the data for determination of the focal length.

Determination of unknown distance of an object and its lateral width

From Eq.(4) we get

$$u = f_c \left(\frac{1}{m} - 1 \right). \quad (6)$$

If u_1 and u_2 are the distances of the object from two positions of the camera with which we photograph the same object with transverse magnification m_1 and m_2

respectively, we get

$$D = f_c \left(\frac{1}{m_2} - \frac{1}{m_1} \right) \quad (7)$$

where $D = u_2 - u_1$. This displacement should be along the line of sight of the camera lens. In terms of the object and image sizes we can write

$$D = f_c \left(\frac{O}{I_2} - \frac{O}{I_1} \right) \quad (8)$$

where O is the size of the object and I_1 and I_2 are the image sizes formed on the camera sensor. Hence we get

$$O = \frac{D}{f_c \left(\frac{1}{I_2} - \frac{1}{I_1} \right)}. \quad (9)$$

In Fig. 1 we show the lens configuration. The lens in the displaced position has been shown with dash-dot marks. In our convention u_1 and u_2 are negative and f_c is positive. If I_1, I_2 are negative quantities, Eq.(9) ensures that the object size turns out positive for all situations. For simplicity in calculation we can write

$$O = \frac{|D|}{f_c \left| \left(\frac{1}{I_2} - \frac{1}{I_1} \right) \right|}. \quad (10)$$

We find the size of the object O using Eq.(10) by determining I_1, I_2 and the distance D since we already know the focal length of the lens. Using Eq.(6) we get the distances of the object from the two positions of the camera when we put m negative. For calculation of the magnitude of the object distance we write Eq.(6) as

$$|u| = f_c \left(\frac{1}{|m|} + 1 \right). \quad (11)$$

Fig.1 Image formation with the displacement of the lens

Experimental Data:

Table I: Data for the focal length f_c of the camera lens (1 pixel= $1.4\mu m$)

Obs. no.	u (cm)	Object width O (mm)	pixel diff.	Image size I (mm)	$m = \frac{I}{O}$	f_c (cm)
1	10	30	953	1.334	0.0445	0.426
2	10	40	1263	1.768	0.0442	0.423
3	20	30	458	0.641	0.0214	0.419
4	50	50	307	0.430	0.00860	0.426
5	100	50	151	0.211	0.00422	0.420
6	100	90	271	0.379	0.00421	0.419
7	200	30	45	0.063	0.00210	0.419
8	200	60	91	0.127	0.00212	0.423
9	200	776	1180	1.652	0.00213	0.425

Experimental Results

In Table I we show data for determining the focal length f_c of the camera lens. Here we give the absolute values of image size, magnification and the object distance. We determine the focal length of the lens for different combinations of object sizes and distances. We get an average focal length $f_c = 4.22 \pm 0.01$ mm. The website¹² gives the focal length of our lens as 4.2mm. In Table II we show the image sizes I_1 and I_2 on the sensor from two positions of the camera. In Table III we show different values of $D = u_2 - u_1$, lateral width of the object calculated using Eq.(10) and its distances from the first position of the camera using Eq.(11). We get the average width of the object as 7.00 ± 0.02 cm where its size from the ruler was 7cm. Values of u_1 in the first column of Table III have been shown only for comparison. Calculated distances match well with the actual distances of the object as shown in this table.

Since we are measuring the image sizes on the sensor from pixel reading, they are very accurate. If we neglect the error in the measurement of I_1 and I_2 in Eq.(10), the error in the estimation of the object width comes mainly from the displacement D and a small error in the focal length of the camera. A small

Table II: Pixel data for the image sizes on the camera sensor from two distances:

Object size from ruler=7cm ; 1 pixel=1.4 μ m

obs	u_1	pixel	I_1	u_2	pixel	I_2
no.	cm	diff. 1	cm	cm	diff. 2	cm
1	10	2235	0.313	50	429	0.0601
2	10	2235	0.313	100	211	0.0295
3	10	2235	0.313	200	106	0.0148
4	20	1074	0.150	50	429	0.0601
5	20	1074	0.150	100	211	0.0295
6	20	1074	0.150	200	106	0.0148
7	50	429	0.0601	100	211	0.0295
8	50	429	0.0601	200	106	0.0148
9	100	211	0.0295	200	106	0.0148

uncertainty in the position of the camera inside the smartphone gets nullified by the displacement D of the phone. So, D gives the actual displacement of the lens. Thus, accuracy of the measurements of the object width and its distance depend mainly on the accuracy of D . We get errors in the object size and its distances from the first position of the camera (u_1) within 3%.

Minimum displacement $D = u_2 - u_1$ required for arbitrary object size and distance

From Eq.(2) we get

$$\delta m = \frac{\delta I}{O}. \quad (12)$$

Taking the minimum detectable change in image size on sensor = R , the minimum detectable change in magnification δm_{min} will be,

$$\delta m_{min} = \frac{R}{O} \quad (13)$$

which is a dimensionless number. From Eq.(3) we get

$$\frac{dm}{du} = -\frac{\frac{1}{f}}{(1 + \frac{u}{f})^2}. \quad (14)$$

Table III: Data for displacement D , Object width obtained using Eq.(10) and Object distances obtained using Eq.(11): Object size from ruler = 7cm

obs	u_1	D	Object width	dist.
no.	cm	cm	cm	cm
1	10	40	7.05	9.93
2	10	90	6.95	9.79
3	10	190	6.99	9.85
4	20	30	7.13	20.5
5	20	80	6.96	20.0
6	20	180	7.00	20.1
7	50	50	6.86	48.6
8	50	150	6.98	49.4
9	100	100	7.04	101.1

For $|u| \gg f$

$$\delta m = -\frac{f}{u^2} du. \quad (15)$$

So the minimum shift in position before the second shot is taken should be

$$\delta u = \frac{u^2}{f} \delta m_{min}. \quad (16)$$

Here, we have shown only the magnitude of δu as our displacement D can be both towards or away from the object. In order to find the height and distance of a 50m high building at a distance of 1km, one has to move a minimum of $\delta u = \frac{10^6 m^2}{4.22mm} \frac{1.4}{50 \times 10^6} = 6.6m$ assuming a clear camera sight. Eq.(13) has been used for δm_{min} .

Even without knowing the actual distance and height of the object one can guess with the help of Eq.(16), by how much one should move to take the second shot so that one gets an appreciable difference between I_1 and I_2 . If one measures the displacement D accurately, one should get an accurate measure of the distance and height of the object. Students may find it interesting to determine the distance and height of far-off tall trees, hillocks and similar other objects just by

taking photographs from two positions with their hand-held smartphone cameras. Following the method described in this paper one may find an alternative way to standard methods of measuring small as well as large length scales. This new method may be easier and accurate.

References

1. Jun Wang and Wenqing Sun, "Measuring the focal length of a camera lens in a smart-phone with a ruler," *Phys.Teach.* **57**,54 (2019).
2. Antoine Girod, Nicolas-Alexandre Goy, Alexandre Vilquin, and Ulysse Delabre, "Studying ray optics with a smartphone." *Phys.Teach.* **58**,133(2020).
3. Jack Freeland, Venkata Rao Krishnamurthi, and Yong Wang, " Learning the lens equation using water and smartphone/tablets," *Phys. Teach.* **58**, 360 (2020).
4. Mickey D Kutzner, and Samantha Snelling, " Measuring magnification of virtual images using digital cameras," *Phys. Teach.* **54**, 503 (2016).
5. Timo Hergemoller, and Daniel Laumann, "Smartphone magnification attachment:Microscope or magnifying glass," *Phys.Teach.* **55**,361 (2017).
6. A.Pons et al., "Learning optics using a smartphone," in *ETOP 2013 Proceedings*, (Optical Society of America,2013),paper EWP13.
7. Shangwen Chen et al., "Single-image distance measurement by a smart mobile device," In *IEEE Transactions on cybernatics*, December 2017.
8. Suraphol Laotrakunchai et al., "Measurement of size and distance of objects using mobile devices," *International conference on signal-image technology and internet-based systems* (2013).
9. Jesus J.Barreiro et al., "Diffraction by electronic components of everyday use," *Am.J.Phys.* **82** 257 (2014).

10. <https://www.kimovil.com/en/apple-iphone-12-mini/camera>
11. <https://www.gsmarena.com/apple-iphone-12-mini-10510.php>
12. <https://www.metadata2go.com/>